

Psychological Well-being and Quality of Life among Adults: A Correlational Study

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Psychological well-being encompasses several factors such as self-esteem, self-efficacy, interpersonal and intrapersonal relationships, life satisfaction, and a sense of psychological happiness, health, and accomplishment. Quality of life denotes the collection of desires that, when fulfilled, contribute to an individual's happiness or satisfaction. To assess the relationship between psychological well-being and quality of life among male and female adults. A sample of 300 adults aged 20-40 years was selected using purposive-cum-incident sampling methods. Psychological well-being was assessed using the Psychological Well-Being Scale developed by Sisodia and Choudhary in 2012, while quality of life was measured using the Quality of Life Scale developed by Sharma and Nasreen in 2014. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults.

Keywords: Psychological, well-being, quality of life, adults, correlational study

Psychological well-being refers to a state in which individuals experience positive emotions and feelings of happiness (Diener, 2000). Self-acceptance, positive relationships with others, autonomy, personal development, environmental mastery, and purpose of life are the six components of Carol Ryff's six-factor model of psychological well-being (Ryff et al., 2010). Individuals with lower psychological well-being who perceive high levels of stress may experience mood disorders like anxiety and depression (Gladstone et al., 2004). Additionally, emotional control, social interactions, physical health, and cognitive performance have all been linked to psychological well-being (Huppert, 2009). Yogic approaches provide comprehensive engagement with multiple dimensions of well-being, offering a holistic framework for achieving and maintaining optimal health and happiness (Park, 2020).

There are two important components to psychological well-being. The first concerns the degree to which people feel happy and feel good. This dimension is often referred to as subjective well-being (Diener, 2000). Consequently, reduced levels of psychosocial well-being may increase the risk of serious health conditions, such as cardiovascular disease, impaired glucose regulation (e.g., diabetes), and compromised immune functioning (Chandola et al., 2008). The theory of psychological well-being suggests that early experiences and inherent personality traits form the foundation of an individual's well-being (Anglim et al., 2020). It represents an overall state of mental and physical health (Mahindru et al., 2023). Positive social interactions, autonomy, environmental mastery, self-acceptance, a sense of purpose in life, and personal development are all

components of psychological well-being, which encompasses emotional health and general functioning (Van Dierendonck et al., 2023). From this perspective, psychological well-being extends beyond mere happiness or pleasure, although these elements are important. Instead, it reflects a eudaimonic orientation that emphasizes personal growth, meaning, and self-actualization (Michalos, 2014). It also includes individuals' outlook on life, life satisfaction, physical health, and mental health (Dhanabhakya et al., 2023). Professionals in a variety of industries where quality of life is important interpret the phrase differently. Costanza et al. define it as "the degree to which objective human needs are met in relation to individual or collective perceptions of subjective well-being" (Costanza et al., 2008). It is impossible to evaluate quality of life using a single metric, and it frequently interacts with ideas like well-being, social functioning, disability, and social support (Albrecht & Fitzpatrick, 1994). Despite worries about how subjective quality of life evaluation is, it remains widely utilized, primarily due to cost considerations in research (Jacobson et al., 1997).

A person's well-being and contentment in a variety of areas are all included in the broad and multifaceted idea of quality of life (Panzini et al., 2017). The World Health Organization provides an official definition, describing it as follows: "Quality of life is an individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns" (WHO, 1997). According to Teoli et al. (2023), quality of life includes one's physical, mental, and spiritual well-being as well as relationships, education, employment, social standing, wealth, a sense of safety and security, independence, decision-making autonomy, social belonging, and physical surroundings.

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Review of Literature

Manchana (2023) aimed to investigate subjective wellness, psychological well-being, and related factors associated with their quality of life in elderly individuals. The result found that there were positively related to quality of life and psychological well-being ($p \leq 0.01$).

Alyami et al. (2021) investigated the impact of COVID-19 dread on adults' quality of life and mental health. The findings revealed a direct association between increased fear of COVID-19 and reduced mental well-being, which was linked to lower quality of life. Notably, a direct association was observed between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults.

Uzaina (2019) conducted a study to assess the quality of life and psychological well-being in both public and private employees. A study randomly selected 100 employees, with 50 from each sector. The study further identified a strong and favorable relationship between many aspects of psychological well-being and quality of life.

Bennecke et al. (2017) investigated the correlation between overall health status, quality of life, and well-being among elderly individuals. A study shows a strong and favorable relationship between quality of life and well-being. If health status is overall good, then well-being and quality of life are also increased.

Verma (2008) conducted a study investigating the Senior citizens' subjective well-being and quality of life in working and non-working conditions across rural and urban settings. The results showed that there were few health issues among the older individuals, with greater satisfaction with the future and an overall better quality of life. Rural elderly individuals reported more physical health issues, while urban elderly participants expressed higher satisfaction with the past. Rural elderly individuals showed greater satisfaction with the future. Urban elderly participants experienced more independence, better social relations, a favourable environment, and an overall better quality of life compared to those in rural areas. However, no significant differences were observed between working and non-working elderly individuals.

Aim of the Study

To assess the relationship between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults.

Hypothesis of the Study

There would be a significant correlation between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults.

Method

Participants

The sample comprised 300 ($N=300$) adults, and the ages ranged from 20 to 40 years. The samples were drawn from different locations in Patna. Incidental cum Purposive sampling methods were used for the selection of the sample, using structured questionnaires. Participants were instructed to mark the tick boxes corresponding to their responses. Confidentiality of responses was ensured, and the ethical guidelines of the APA were rigorously adhered to while working with human participants in the study.

Inclusion Criteria of the Sample

- Age range of 20-40 years
- Residents of Patna
- Without any additional chronic illnesses.

Exclusion Criteria of Sample

- Any history of a psychotic disorder
- Living outside Patna
- Age range <20-40> years

- With any additional chronic disease

Research Design

This study used both a correlational design. Psychological Well-being and Quality of Life were identified as dependent variables. The selection of a correlational design aligns with the research objectives, as it enables examining relationships between variables without experimental manipulation.

Measures

The following tools were used in the study to collect the data for the sample.

Psychological Well-Being Scale: Psychological well-being was assessed using the Psychological Well-Being Scale (PWBSAA) developed by Sisodia and Choudhary in 2012. The scale consists of 50 positively worded items designed to measure five dimensions: satisfaction, efficiency, sociability, mental health, and interpersonal relations. Responses are recorded on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1). Total scores range from 50 to 250, with higher scores indicating greater levels of psychological well-being. The scale is suitable for individuals aged 16 to 60 years. The instrument has demonstrated good reliability, with a test-retest reliability coefficient of .87 and an internal consistency coefficient of .90, both significant at the .01 level.

Quality of Life Scale: Quality of life was assessed using the Quality of Life Scale (QOLSSNN) developed by Sharma and Nasreen in 2014. The scale consists of 42 items covering eleven domains: life satisfaction, goals and motivation, spirituality, happiness, hopes and wishes, stress reduction, frustration/depression/anxiety, adjustment, physical well-being and self-care, effectiveness/efficiency of self, and personal development/personal evolution. Of the total items, 34 are positively worded and 8 are negatively worded. Responses are recorded on a three-point scale: Always, Seldom, and Never. Positively worded items are scored 3, 2, and 1, respectively, while negatively worded items are reverse-scored (1, 2, & 3). The scale has demonstrated acceptable reliability, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients reported as .80 and .82. Face validity of the instrument has also been established. The scale is suitable for use with adult populations.

Demographic Information Sheet. A demographic information sheet was developed for the purpose of the present study to collect participants' background information. The sheet includes items related to name, age, gender, educational status, and socio-economic status.

Procedure

Prior approval was obtained from the relevant authority, and data were collected using a structured questionnaire through incidental-cum-purposive sampling. Informed consent was secured after establishing rapport with participants, who completed the Psychological Well-being and Quality of Life scales (average time: 20-30 minutes) without time constraints. Responses were recorded using tick boxes, with strict confidentiality and anonymity maintained throughout. Data were used solely for research purposes and scored as per the manual. Some challenges included incomplete or blank responses and non-return of questionnaires.

Results and Discussion

“There would be a significant correlation between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults.”

The result table shows the Pearson correlation between Psychological Well-being and Quality of life among adults.

Table 1

Showing Correlation between Psychological Well-being and Quality of Life among Adults

Variable		Psychological well-being	Quality of life
Psychological Well-being	Pearson Correlation	1	.901**
	N	300	300
Quality of life	Pearson Correlation	.901**	1
	N	300	300

Note. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

Table 1 presents a Pearson correlation between psychological well-being and quality of life of 0.901, which is significant at the 0.01 level, and the total number of samples (N) is 300. This strong positive correlation (0.901) indicates a significant association between psychological well-being and quality of life. Specifically, it suggests that individuals with higher levels of psychological well-being also have higher levels of quality of life, while those with lower psychological well-being have lower quality of life. The correlation shows that the strong association between an individual's psychological well-being and quality of life. Hence, the hypothesis "There would be a significant correlation between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults" is accepted.

This result is consistent with prior findings linked to psychological well-being and quality of life among adults. The results revealed that they were positively correlated to psychological well-being and quality of life ($p \leq 0.01$). The study highlighted the interconnectedness between evolving family and social relationships and the psychological well-being of older adults, emphasizing an immediate public health issue (Manchana, 2023). According to Alyami et al. (2021), findings revealed a direct correlation between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults. A study shows a significant and positive correlation between quality of life and various dimensions of psychological well-being (Uzaina, 2019; Bennecke et al., 2017). This statement suggests that the current research findings contradict the results of prior studies conducted by Verma (2008) who found that there was no substantial association between quality of life and psychological well-being.

Therefore, the current study revealed that psychological well-being was positively associated with quality of life among adults; hence, the hypothesis "There would be a significant correlation between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults" is proved.

Figure 1

The Graphical Representation of Correlation between Psychological Well-being and Quality of Life among Adults

Figure 1 presents a line graph showing the correlation between psychological well-being variables and quality of life among adults. Blue line describes psychological well-being, while the saffron line represents quality of life. Psychological well-being and quality of life showed a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.901. Thus, a line graph describes a positive correlation found between psychological well-being and quality of life variables.

Conclusion

A significant positive relationship existed between psychological well-being and quality of life among adults. It means that if one variable increases, the other variable also tends to increase. In this context, it implies that individuals who report higher levels of psychological well-being also tend to report higher levels of quality of life, while those with lower psychological well-being tend to report lower quality of life.

Limitations of the Study

- The sample size of this study is 300 adults, which is limited and may not represent all Adults.
- The sample was a limited age group 20-40year olds.
- The study was delimited to the Patna district of Bihar.

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